

Article

Data-Driven Defrost-on-Demand Scheduling in Reefer Ships: A Predictive Maintenance Framework Using Real-World Sensor Data

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Abstract

Defrost cycles in shipboard refrigeration plants are typically initiated on fixed schedules or by operator judgement, which can lead to unnecessary energy use and temperature variability during the transport of frozen products. This study proposes a data-driven predictive maintenance approach to trigger defrost on demand in a merchant reefer vessel carrying frozen tuna. A total of 76,692 operational records from cargo-hold air coolers and holds were analysed, including delivery and return air temperatures, hold air temperature and relative humidity. The records were modelled to show their behaviour under real voyage conditions. The modelled strategy indicates that 66.55% of defrost cycles performed during the study period were unnecessary, suggesting substantial scope to reduce defrost frequency and associated disturbances. These findings demonstrate the feasibility of implementing machine learning (ML)-based decision support for maritime refrigeration. This enables defrost-on-demand scheduling, which has the potential to enhance operational efficiency while supporting product quality, sustainability and traceability in the frozen tuna supply chain.

Keywords: big data; defrost-on-demand; data-driven marine systems; predictive maintenance; reefer ship; supervised machine learning

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Reefer ships represent a critical point in the cold chain of frozen tuna transportation. After tuna are caught by purse seiners, the fish are frozen and stored onboard until unloading, either landing or—more often—transshipment to a reefer, commonly employed for the transportation of frozen tuna [1–3]. A key challenge for companies engaged in tuna fishing is to ensure that the fish delivered to canneries is in the best possible condition for processing and sale. If the cold chain is maintained, frozen fish will retain the same nutritional properties as fresh fish [4].

On freezer tuna seiners, fish are frozen in brine straight after capture; initially to a temperature of $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and then to $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to ensure that the fish retain their quality characteristics. Subsequently, the fish are subjected to a dry cooling process, until they are unloaded onto a reefer ship and transported in bulk to the port of destination [5]. Although only a few minutes are required to unload a single frozen tuna from the freezing vat to the

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hold of the merchant vessel, the entire unloading process can take several days [6]. Both tuna freezer vessels and reefer ships are constructed and equipped in accordance with the regulations and standards of the United States Department of Agriculture [7] to ensure the quality and food safety of perishable food products during transportation [8].

In the context of the global tuna value chain, the concept of traceability, defined as “the ability to track and trace tuna or tuna products through all stages of production and distribution”, encompasses the entire production and distribution process, from catch to consumption and enables the effective management of potential risks [9,10]. The “cold chain” is defined as “a series of actions and equipment applied to maintain a product within a specified low-temperature range from harvest/production to consumption” [11]. Maintaining the correct temperature for frozen fish prevents the growth and development of bacteria and the deterioration of fishery products at all stages of the cold chain. It is essential to record the temperature of the surrounding environment, the cold rooms, and the product itself.

During a defrost cycle, the refrigeration of the vessel’s cargo spaces is interrupted, and this has an impact on the temperature of the fish. It is therefore essential to optimise the defrost process to minimise such stoppages or interruptions [12]. In this regard, the deployment of artificial intelligence (AI) to automate or initiate this process presents opportunities to enhance the traceability of these operations. For the air coolers in holds to operate effectively, a key factor is the operation of their fans. It is crucial to eliminate any frost that forms on air cooler fins, as it reduces their capacity to cool the air circulating in the vessel’s cargo space, to keep it at the optimum temperature for transporting the fish. Additionally, it is of interest to consider the environmental impact of maintaining the cold chain, which is primarily through energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions, contributing to climate change. As early as 2008, Coulomb [13] estimated that 15% of global electricity was used in refrigeration processes during the storage, transport and sale of refrigerated foods. This figure rose to 17% in 2018 [14] due to the electricity consumption of air conditioning equipment [15].

From this perspective, it is essential to optimise defrost cycles for reducing energy consumption in refrigeration systems, and the monitoring and processing of data from such systems is crucial for this process [16]. If defrost starts later than is optimal, more ice accumulates, and defrosting takes longer and consumes more energy. Conversely, if the process is too short, the frost will not be fully eliminated, and the cooling capacity and efficiency of the system will be impaired. A study on air source heat pumps [17] demonstrated that initiating defrosting 10 min before or after the optimal time point resulted in a 32% to 56% reduction in the coefficient of performance (COP) and a 37% to 54% reduction in heating capacity.

In the type of ship refrigeration plant under analysis, it is common practice to rely on the experience of the chief engineers and engine officers who operate, maintain and monitor the equipment, as they know the system best, to decide on the timing of the start and end of the defrost cycle, despite the process being automated. Energy is consumed during the defrost cycle to heat the brine and to restore the air in the hold to the required transport temperature following defrosting. If defrosting is only conducted when necessary, fewer cycles are needed, resulting in both energy savings and improved product quality [18]. Further, it would be useful to be able to predict when it is appropriate to start the defrosting process considering the suitability of each defrost.

The introduction of the latest technological developments offered by Maintenance 4.0 in the operation and maintenance of the equipment installed on ships is a paradigm shift. In the maritime field, the planned maintenance system is the most commonly used maintenance strategy, and it is widely acknowledged that the human factor plays a pivotal

role in this approach [19]. This is why we propose the use of a machine learning (ML) technique to determine the optimal starting point, thereby minimising unnecessary visits to a ship's cargo hold to check on the condition of the equipment and cargo. Any opening of the hold lets in humid air, in turn, increasing the likelihood of ice generation, and it causes the fans that control air circulation in the holds to shut down, which affects the temperature at which fish are transported.

The advent of "Industry 4.0" has had a significant impact on industrial maintenance strategies, with a notable shift in the approach to predictive maintenance driven by the emergence of advanced technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT) [20] that enables real-time monitoring allowing for the identification of patterns and anomalies that can predict potential failures and the formulation of recommendations regarding maintenance [21]. The integration of AI methodologies, such as ML and neural networks, into maintenance strategies makes it possible to anticipate potential equipment failures and schedule interventions, thereby ensuring the reliability, efficiency and cost-effectiveness of the equipment [22]. It is therefore possible to speak of a new paradigm in refrigeration, which we can call "Refrigeration 4.0".

1.2. Literature Review

A wide range of defrost control strategies have been proposed in the literature for refrigeration and heat-pump systems. Conventional approaches include reverse-cycle hot gas systems, off-cycle methods and electric defrost [18,23–25]. Control and automation techniques are used to adjust defrost times. Currently, the most common ways to regulate the start of the cycle are to use a defrost interval timer or timing control [18,24] or a defrost schedule [24]. Alternatively, some systems consider the maximum thermostat runtime, which accounts for the accumulated refrigeration time between defrosts [24], or the defrost process can be initiated manually or externally via a digital input, application, or a defrost start/stop button on a display [24]. End of the cycle techniques include timing control, a defrost or discharge temperature sensor, or temperature control, or manual defrost termination [18,24]. These methods are robust and simple to implement but are poorly adapted to variable operating conditions such as fluctuating ambient humidity, door openings or changing load profiles.

To overcome these limitations, sensor-based on-demand defrost control approaches have been employed, based on sensing the air pressure differential across the evaporator, temperature difference between air and evaporator surface, or fan power, as well as photo-optic or fibre optic sensors. Other studies have focused on directly measuring frost thickness to control the start of the defrost cycle. While such approaches can be effective under controlled laboratory conditions, they typically require specific operational setups or additional sensing hardware that may not be feasible in real shipboard machinery [26]. For instance, Sun et al. [27] propose a defrost control technique based on greyscale graph theory that uses image processing to quantify the amount of ice in the evaporators of a cold store in a laboratory in a controlled environment. Image processing is combined with fractal theory in another experimental method proposed by Miao et al. [28]. The measurement of frost accumulation on the evaporator appears to be a viable method for initiating the defrosting process. Lima et al. [29] emphasize the need to develop sensors that account for external factors such as frost morphology, density, translucency and electrical properties. However, integrating such specialised sensors into existing commercial refrigeration systems with minimal design alterations and cost remains challenging [18,30,31].

Concurrently, a growing body of research has explored the potential of adaptive, data-driven defrost strategies within the contexts of both domestic and commercial refrigeration. In the field of domestic refrigerators, Ghadiri Modarres et al. [32] propose an adaptive

methodology in which the time and frequency of defrosting are adjusted according to parameters such as the cumulative running time of the compressor and the time the refrigerator doors have been open.

Industrial solutions such as Danfoss controllers [24] and COFRICO’s Gradhoc [33] implement adaptive defrost logic that can cancel scheduled defrosts or trigger them based on indicators of reduced airflow. These solutions leverage IoT, digital twins and AI. These approaches illustrate the potential of using operational data to transition from fixed schedules to condition-based or demand-driven defrost. The development of “Refrigeration 4.0” requires AI techniques such as deep reinforcement learning. In the defrost process, this technique enables the system to adapt dynamically to changing environmental conditions. The controller is capable of making autonomous decisions and optimising them without the need for human intervention, such as the ML technique described by Klingebiel et al. [34] for heat pumps, where the controller learns to identify optimal cycle start times through a trial-and-error process by collecting data on air, condensing and evaporating temperatures using standard sensors.

Overall, the existing literature shows that (i) defrost timing has a critical impact on system efficiency and capacity; (ii) many on-demand defrost strategies rely on additional or specialised sensors or are validated only in highly controlled environments; and (iii) predictive maintenance and ML are increasingly used in refrigeration and HVAC (Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning), but mainly in stationary installations such as buildings, cold rooms or industrial plants rather than shipboard systems. Following a comprehensive review of the literature on defrost control strategies, the most relevant studies have been synthesised in Table 1.

Table 1. Representative defrost control strategies in literature.

Study/Year	System Type	Defrost Control Strategy	Additional Sensors	Environment	AI/Data-Driven
Tassou et al. (2001) [18]	Open multideck display cabinet	Time-based defrost with HR-based on-demand potential	No	Laboratory/test rig	No
Ghadiri et al. (2016) [32]	Domestic refrigerator	Adaptive schedule (operational data)	No	Experimental	Rule based/adaptive)
Chung et al. (2019) [31]	Air source heat pump	On-demand, Δp /frost tracking	Differential pressure/frost sensor	Laboratory	No
de Aguiar et al. (2019) [29]	General vapor-compression evaporators	On-demand/frost measurement	Dedicated frost sensors	Conceptual/laboratory	No
Danfoss (2020) [24]	Commercial refrigeration	Adaptive/condition-based	No	Commercial refrigeration	Rule based/adaptive)
Li et al. (2020) [30]	Air source heat pump	Optimised timing (model-based)	No	Field	Data-driven
Miao et al. (2022) [28]	Air source heat pump/Experimental evaporator	On-demand T-H-I defrost based on image processing and fractal theory	Camera, image processing	Experimental/test rig	No
Sun et al. (2022) [27]	Cold store	On-demand, gray-scale image/vision-based frost tracking	Camera, image processing	Laboratory	No
Klingebiel et al. (2023) [34]	Air source heat pump	Deep reinforcement learning (DRL)/self-optimising/on-demand	No	Laboratory/simulation	Yes (DRL)
Gradhoc (2024) [33]	Commercial refrigeration	Predictive/adaptive	No	Commercial refrigeration	Data-driven

As outlined in Table 1, some experimental on-demand defrost strategies are contingent upon supplementary sensing hardware and are substantiated within the confines of controlled laboratory settings. Conversely, industrial adaptive controllers employed in commercial and industrial refrigeration systems are predominantly designed to oversee stationary facilities, such as cold stores or supermarket installations. In contrast, the present study address defrost control in shipboard frozen tuna transport using machine learning and relying solely on existing shipboard instrumentation in an operational reefer vessel. This quantitative synthesis underscores the research gap that the present study aims to fill by developing and benchmarking a supervised classifier for defrost validity based exclusively on standard temperature and humidity sensors in a real maritime environment.

Building on these observations, the proposed methodology involves data collection from sensors already integrated into the refrigeration system of interest, which eliminates additional costs and simplifies the process, while also avoiding any disruption to the equipment or machinery. Although the reefer's refrigeration system incorporates automated defrost control, the operation could be improved by determining the optimal time for initiating the defrost cycle. The prevailing practice on the reefer ship is to control the start and duration of the process manually. It is important to note that the holds of a vessel are not entirely airtight. Therefore, even if a tween-deck space is closed, the opening of a space above it, during loading or unloading processes, for example, can result in fluctuations in the temperature of the air in an entire hold. Further, as the fish reach their designated transport temperature, moisture is released, which in turn affects the surrounding environment.

The technique proposed in this paper is based on the prediction of a dependent variable, which determines the suitability of the defrosting process, as a function of the independent variables measured. Once the validity of a defrost in the cargo space has been established by analysing the appropriate data, an algorithm—in this case, a classifier—can be developed using ML techniques. This will enable the system to determine whether it is appropriate to start a defrosting process based on the characteristics of the input data. The implementation of a defrost-on-demand system has the potential to reduce the number of cycles, thereby leading to energy savings. It should be noted that the plant under study is already in operation, rather than in its design stage. Consequently, this represents a preliminary step towards enhancing its efficiency.

The primary objective of this study is to ascertain the optimal timing for starting the defrosting process of the refrigeration plant aboard a vessel engaged in the transportation of frozen tuna, as part of a predictive maintenance strategy. The incorporation of novel data into the management of defrosting has various implications, including the enhancement of defrosting process efficiency, the prediction of necessary defrosting events, and the automation of defrosting initiation and termination. Currently, the process is started manually at the operator's discretion and scheduled to last for a designated time. The study explores whether it may be possible to reduce the number of defrost cycles and the duration of the process and guide the selection of variables that indicate the need to perform defrosting.

To the authors' knowledge, there is a paucity of studies that leverage machine learning to implement defrost-on-demand control in shipboard refrigeration systems for frozen tuna transport using only existing operational sensors and without modifying the plant hardware. This study addresses this gap by (i) developing an event-based feature engineering strategy from existing shipboard sensors (temperatures and relative humidity) using 12–36 h time windows and (ii) applying supervised classification to predict defrost validity (CLASE = 1 required/valid; CLASE = 0 non-required/avoidable) and benchmarking tuned models.

The study is guided by the following questions: (i) which sensor-derived features are most informative for discriminating necessary from unnecessary defrosts; (ii) to what extent can a supervised classifier distinguish required versus non-required defrost events under real operating conditions; and (iii) which tuned model provides the best trade-off between missed required defrosts (FNs) and unnecessary defrost triggers (FPs) for operational deployment?

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Case Study

The case study focuses on the refrigeration plant on a reefer ship (see Table 2 for further details) equipped to transport fruit and frozen goods, primarily frozen tuna, as bulk or palletised cargo. The vessel has been classified as “REF-CARGO QUICKFREEZE,” which indicates that it meets the operational standards and has the design and equipment suitable for the quick-freezing of fish and the transport of cargo [35].

Table 2. Vessel characteristics.

Characteristics	Value
Construction year	2001
Shipbuilder	H. J. Barreras (Spain)
Vessel type	Reefer ship
Bureau Veritas Classification	Class I, ✕HULL, ✕MACH, UNRESTRICTED NAVIGATION, REFRIGERATED CARGO SHIP, ✕AUT-UMS, ✕REF-CARGO QUICKFREEZE.
Total length	132.9 m
Moulded breadth	18.80 m
Summer draft	8.00 m
Gross tonnage	7207 T
Deadweight tonnage	7710 DWT
Refrigerated cargo capacity	8800 m ³

Note: The construction mark (✕) signifies that the item to which it is appended (e.g. HULL/MACH) was constructed in accordance with the Bureau Veritas survey for the initial allocation of class.

The vessel has four cargo holds, which are subdivided into tween decks. Holds 1 and 2 are divided into three tween decks, while holds 3 and 4 are divided into four. Consequently, the cargo space comprises 14 cargo compartments (1a–c, 2a–c, 3a–d and 4a–d), each with its own separate air circulation system and 6 independently insulated temperature zones (1a–1b–1c, 2a–2b–2c, 3a–3b, 3c–3d, 4a–4b and 4c–4d), as shown in Figure 1. Each temperature zone is equipped with a dedicated brine recirculation system. Compartments 1c, 2c, 3d and 4d correspond to the hold plan, which represents the lowest part of the ship’s cargo area.

The refrigerated vessel is equipped with a refrigeration plant (see Table 3) designed to allow the simultaneous operation of all four holds. The refrigeration plant comprises three brine chiller units, each with a capacity of 816 kW, which operate on ammonia (NH₃). The chiller units are modular and can be operated independently depending on demand. The cooling system is indirect [36]; that is, the secondary refrigerant (brine) is cooled in a heat exchanger by the primary coolant (ammonia) and then circulated through the air coolers in the holds.

Figure 1. Temperature zones and compartments of the holds.

Table 3. Cooling system features.

Characteristics	Value
Net volume	328,500 ft ³ /9203 m ³
Ambient air	35 °C/70% HR
Sea water temperature	32 °C
Insulation	K = 0.52 W/m ² ·k
Cooling system	Indirect
Primary coolant	NH ₃ -R-717
Secondary refrigerant	Brine Cl ₂ Ca
Defrost	Hot brine
Manufacturer	Grenco Ibérica, S.A. (A Coruña, Spain)
Classification	Bureau Veritas
Regulations	United States Department of Agriculture

The brine distribution system comprises two circuits: a primary circuit, which is used for cooling and defrosting, and a secondary circuit, which is used for defrosting the trays below the coolers. The primary circuit is used for the circulation of cold brine, while the secondary circuit is used for the circulation of hot brine, which is employed for defrosting. The refrigeration plant is operated by an automated control system that facilitates data acquisition, monitoring and regulation of the equipment. It can be used for monitoring variables of interest, with reports generated at a pre-set time interval.

Each compartment is equipped with two air coolers, which facilitate air change at a rate of 45 times per hour. These coolers are situated against the bulkhead in a vertical air duct, with axial fans in casings mounted above them. This assembly is frequently referred to as a “cooling battery”. The fans facilitate forced circulation of air within the hold, whereby the temperature is reduced as heat is transferred to the cold brine that is circulated within the cooler, as illustrated in Figure 2. The cool air circulating around the hold removes heat from the fish, thereby reducing its temperature. Following its circulation around the fish, the air returns to the heat exchanger at a higher temperature, is cooled and is blown back into the hold. The data obtained from the air temperature sensors provides insight into how the cargo responds to the cooling supplied. When the holds are being cooled, the delivery sensor indicates a lower temperature than the return sensor.

2.2. Defrost

The hold atmosphere contains water vapour, the amount of which varies depending on the capacity of air to hold water at a given temperature. The term RH is used to describe the amount of water vapour in the atmosphere. It is calculated as the percentage of water vapour at a given temperature compared to the amount that could be present if the atmosphere were saturated [37]. When air is saturated, that is to say, when it is unable to hold any more water vapour (100% RH), condensation occurs if the temperature falls;

this is called the dew point. Should a heat exchanger cool to a temperature below the dew point of the surrounding atmosphere, water will condense on surrounding surfaces, forming ice or frost, especially on the cooler. As described by Léoni et al. [38], there is a substantial body of research on frost formation. In the context of a ship's hold, due to its open connection to the external atmosphere, moisture-laden air is introduced into the hold during loading or unloading, and this results in frost formation.

Figure 2. Forced air circulation within a compartment.

It is not possible to achieve optimal cooling by just gradually lowering the temperature until the excess humidity has been completely removed. Frost building up on a cooler increases its thermal resistance to heat transfer and decreases its cooling capacity. The accumulation of frost on both the pipes and fins reduces airflow and causes the fan to operate incorrectly and therefore inefficiently. It is thus imperative to remove the frost from the air coolers by defrosting not only the coil surface but also the drain pans [39].

It is essential to defrost the system to maintain fish quality, thereby minimising reductions in air-cooler performance and blockages caused by ice build-up and decreasing operating times. The formation of ice on the cooler fins reduces heat transfer to the brine circulating in the cooler, and limits the flow of air outside the cooler, in turn decreasing the cooler's efficiency. Additionally, the formation of ice on the drip pans can impair the cooler's performance, as the water in the drain pipes freezes, stopping the melted ice from draining out. It is crucial to ascertain the optimal timing for defrosting, as any delay in starting the process will result in a longer defrosting period, and the optimal length of defrost, and if the duration is insufficient, the cooler will not be completely defrosted, resulting in the progressive accumulation of ice.

The block, tray and cooler fans are regularly inspected for frost formation, with the goal of either correcting the number of scheduled defrosts or manually removing any abnormal accumulation of frost and ice. This results in fluctuations in the air temperature in the compartments, which are detrimental to the maintenance of the facility. It is also important to consider that this process is primarily guided by the expertise and experience of the technicians responsible for operating the plant.

As illustrated in Figure 3, the indirect ammonia–brine refrigeration plant incorporates a configuration of cold-brine and hot-brine circuits that are utilised for the defrosting process of air coolers within the cargo holds. The brine circuit that supplies cold brine to the air coolers during normal operation is utilised to circulate hot brine through the cooling fins and drain pans during defrost. This is achieved by actuating a set of valves located in the brine room.

Figure 3. Cooling and defrosting system with hot brine in the cooling batteries.

The brine system comprises separate expansion tanks for cold and hot brine, located in the upper part of the ship structure. These tanks compensate for volume changes due to temperature variations. Operationally, the defrosting process is initiated in the tray located beneath the cooler, with the objective of eradicating residual ice and frozen water from preceding cycles. This process is then repeated within the heat exchanger block. Initially, hot brine is circulated through the tray circuit and returned to the hot-brine header.

Subsequently, the hot-brine inlet valve to the air cooler (V-2) is opened, and the cold-brine inlet is closed (V-3), so that this is progressively filled with hot brine. In this transient phase, the return flow is directed towards the cold-brine header until the brine outlet temperature reaches approximately 0 °C. At this point, a set of butterfly valves in the brine room switches the discharge from the cold-brine header to the hot-brine header. The installation then enters a defrost mode for the programmed duration (V-5 closed/V-4 open).

The hot-brine temperature is maintained by a closed fresh-water circuit heated by an MGO (Marine Gas Oil)-fired boiler, which keeps the water at approximately 55 °C. This water circulates through a plate heat exchanger, where it heats the brine up to around 52 °C for use during the defrosting process. The end of the defrost cycle can be controlled either by time (a fixed number of defrosts per day) or by the brine return temperature: When the return temperature reaches a high value (of the order of 25 °C), the system indicates that the heat exchanger is fully defrosted. At this point, the hot-brine inlet valve is closed (V-2), the cold-brine inlet valve is reopened (V-3), and the hot-brine supply to the tray (V-1) is also closed, returning the air cooler to normal refrigeration operation. For clarity, the control logic of the hot-brine defrost is summarised in the flowchart shown in Figure 4.

Further, the defrosting process is conducted by temperature zone, in groups of two tween decks in holds 3 (3ab/3cd) and 4 (4ab/4cd), and in groups of three tween decks in holds 1 (1abc) and 2 (2abc). It is possible that defrosting may be required in some of compartments of a zone, but not in others, for example, in compartment 2a, but not in 2b or 2c. This is due to the technical design of the plant and the distribution of the lines, and in

turn, this implies that the entire temperature zone must remain uncooled during defrosting, regardless of the cargo status of each compartment. The system employs the cold-brine pipes to the cargo spaces for the transmission of the hot brine used in the defrosting process. This results in the heating of the cargo spaces and the unnecessary consumption of energy to restore the temperature in the compartments in which this process was not required.

Figure 4. Control logic of the hot-brine defrost cycle.

The automation system that controls the plant allows the user to program certain parameters in order to carry out defrosting in a specific hold. These parameters include the following:

- Time interval between two consecutive defrosts;
- Time required to remove frost from the tray of each cooler;
- Brine return temperature, defined as the temperature at which it is considered that there is no longer any cold brine in the cooler;
- Time for draining the cold brine;
- Temperature of the brine at which defrosting is considered to be complete;
- Duration of the defrosting process;
- Hot-brine return temperature, defined as the temperature at which it is deemed that the hot brine has been completely removed from the cooler;
- Time for draining the hot brine.

The defrosting process is typically started manually, with a duration of between 15 and 25 min. Before the completion of a tween deck loading, the standard procedure is to initiate the defrosting process at the end of each workday; whereas, once a loading is finished and the hold is closed, a defrost is conducted every 6 to 8 h, considering the potential moisture content of the fish. As this moisture decreases, the defrost interval is reduced. Based on the experience of the plant operators, when the temperature at the sensor in the holds reaches $-15\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the defrost interval is reduced to 12 h. Further, once the temperature

reaches $-18\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, defrosts are conducted every 24 h, and when it reaches $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, every 48 h. These guidelines are the result of operational experience and must be considered as such.

To ascertain the need to defrost, the behaviour of the following variables has been taken into account:

- The RH in the compartment varies depending on the port where the ship has carried out or is currently carrying out loading and/or unloading operations. Once the hold has been closed and the air within the hold begins to be cooled, the RH progressively decreases, and, consequently, fewer defrosts are required.
- Delivery temperature (air from the hold cooler): under normal operating conditions, the temperature of the air supplied is lower than that of the return air, but in the presence of frost on the cooler, this delivery air temperature increases by approximately 2 to 3 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.
- Return temperature (air flowing to the hold cooler): when frost is present on the cooler, the temperature of the air supplied tends to become closer to the return air temperature.
- The temperature of the sensors in the holds: when the plant is operating normally, these temperatures follow a downward curve, indicating a progressive decrease in the temperature of the cargo space.

2.3. Data Analysis

To categorise an event as valid or invalid, the raw data are converted into practical information through a series of steps. This allows the raw data obtained from the plant to be transformed into meaningful inputs. The greater the quantity of data obtained, the more potentially accurate the predictions [40]. A key part of this study is to define the problem to be solved and what the analysis hopes to achieve. The necessary data are then acquired, in the case of this study, from sensors in the holds of a ship. These data are then cleaned and processed, as it is rare that data are available in a format that allows for immediate analysis. Specifically, the data are subjected to a process of cleansing, whereby any errors, missing values or duplicate records are removed, and the data are transformed into a format that is suitable for further analysis.

The understanding of the main characteristics of the data through the use of descriptive statistics and graphical representations enables the subsequent identification of patterns or correlations between variables, namely exploratory data analysis [41]. One of the initial stages of exploratory analysis is the graphical representation of the data, which helps identify characteristics, detect patterns or anomalies, relate trends in the behaviour of variables, and draw meaningful conclusions. This visualisation of the data in graphs is a pivotal phase of the process, as it enables the extraction of insights from the examination and collation of data, which serve as the foundation for problem-solving [42], as well as from the monitoring of the equipment, facilitating a more comprehensive understanding of the contextual framework within which the analysis is conducted. In turn, this enables the formulation of well-informed decisions aimed at enhancing the performance of the system of interest, the reefer refrigeration plant, in this study [43]. Ultimately, in light of the problem to be solved and the pre-set objectives, the results are interpreted to decide whether a defrosting process should be initiated in given circumstances. For this analysis, we used the Jupyter Notebook 6.4.11 and the Python 3.9.7 programming language.

2.3.1. Data Acquisition

Field research was conducted to collect data on the operation of the vessel's refrigeration plant during the time interval between loading and unloading operations in different ports. These operations involved transferring the fish to a factory for canning or cold

storage facilities until sale. The data acquisition process was conducted by the automated system that oversaw the refrigeration plant operations between September 2021 and February 2022, collecting data at hourly intervals. This system monitored and recorded the temperatures of the 14 identified zones within the holds, resulting in a total of 5478 files. For each of the compartments, the dataset comprises the variables outlined in Table 4.

Table 4. Variables included in the analysis.

Variable	Units	Measurement Characteristic	Sensor Model	Sensing Element	Tolerance
T_return_SB	°C	Starboard air return temperature *	Danfoss MBT 3250	RTD Pt100 or Pt1000, EN/IEC 60751 (Class B)	$\pm(0.3 + 0.005 \times t)$ °C (Class B)
T_return_PS	°C	Port air return temperature *	Danfoss MBT 3250	RTD Pt100 or Pt1000, EN/IEC 60751 (Class B)	$\pm(0.3 + 0.005 \times t)$ °C (Class B)
T_deliver_SB	°C	Starboard air delivery temperature *	Danfoss MBT 3250	RTD Pt100 or Pt1000, EN/IEC 60751 (Class B)	$\pm(0.3 + 0.005 \times t)$ °C (Class B)
T_deliver_PS	°C	Port air delivery temperature *	Danfoss MBT 3250	RTD Pt100 or Pt1000, EN/IEC 60751 (Class B)	$\pm(0.3 + 0.005 \times t)$ °C (Class B)
T_pulp_1	°C	Temperature sensor no. 1 *	Danfoss MBT 5111	Type K thermocouple, IEC/EN 60584-2 (Class 2)	± 2.5 °C or $\pm 0.0075 \times t$ (Class 2)
T_pulp_2	°C	Temperature sensor no. 2 *	Danfoss MBT 5111	Type K thermocouple, IEC/EN 60584-2 (Class 2)	± 2.5 °C or $\pm 0.0075 \times t$ (Class 2)
T_pulp_3	°C	Temperature sensor no. 3 *	Danfoss MBT 5111	Type K thermocouple, IEC/EN 60584-2 (Class 2)	± 2.5 °C or $\pm 0.0075 \times t$ (Class 2)
T_pulp_4	°C	Temperature sensor no. 4 *	Danfoss MBT 5111	Type K thermocouple, IEC/EN 60584-2 (Class 2)	± 2.5 °C or $\pm 0.0075 \times t$ (Class 2)
T_pulp_5	°C	Temperature sensor no. 5 *	Danfoss MBT 5111	Type K thermocouple, IEC/EN 60584-2 (Class 2)	± 2.5 °C or $\pm 0.0075 \times t$ (Class 2)
T_pulp_6	°C	Temperature sensor no. 6 *	Danfoss MBT 5111	Type K thermocouple, IEC/EN 60584-2 (Class 2)	± 2.5 °C or $\pm 0.0075 \times t$ (Class 2)
T_pulp_7	°C	Temperature sensor no. 7 *	Danfoss MBT 5111	Type K thermocouple, IEC/EN 60584-2 (Class 2)	± 2.5 °C or $\pm 0.0075 \times t$ (Class 2)
RH	%	Percent relative humidity *	---	---	---
Cargo space	---	Hold compartment **	---	---	---

* Continuous quantitative variable; ** nominal qualitative variable.

The temperature measurements were obtained using Danfoss industrial sensors. Air-cooler delivery and return air temperatures (T_deliver, T_return) were measured with Danfoss MBT 3250 sensors, which are compliant with EN 60751 and typically supplied with Class B tolerances ($\pm(0.3 + 0.005 \times t)$ °C), where t is the temperature of medium. The measurement of hold temperatures (T_pulp) was obtained using Danfoss MBT 5111 sensors, which are based on a Type K thermocouple that complies with EN 60584-2 Class 2 tolerances ($\pm(2.5 \pm 0.0075 \times t)$ °C). The sensor tolerances are reported here as a practical proxy for measurement uncertainty at the sensing-element level. In the absence of a dedicated calibration or a full uncertainty budget for the present dataset, it is possible that the overall measurement uncertainty of the acquisition chain (including wiring, signal conditioning and data logging) may exceed the nominal tolerance of the sensing element.

In addition to the manufacturer tolerances reported above, the hold temperature sensors are routinely checked on board against a calibrated reference “master” thermometer (Testo 105/108) prior to each cargo loading operation. The chief engineer and crew pay particular attention to sensors that show signs of drift or malfunction, which are then replaced as part of a preventive maintenance programme. The reference Testo thermometers are themselves subject to annual certification by an accredited body recognised by the relevant sanitary authorities or by Bureau Veritas. This ensures the traceability of the temperature measurements. Sanitary authorities periodically perform detailed inspections of the refrigeration plant and cargo spaces to verify their suitability before issuing or

renewing the sanitary certificate required for operation. In addition, surveys conducted by Bureau Veritas confirm compliance of the refrigeration installation with the applicable classification rules.

A total of 5478 files were generated by the system, resulting in the creation of a database containing 76,692 records. Similarly, data were available on the defrosting processes, including the date, the compartment in which defrosting is carried out and the start time of the process or event. A total of 1701 records were collected manually. In addition, data have been gathered on the status of the hold and the various compartments in order to ascertain whether they are open or closed. The data in question are listed in Table 5 and are derived from the “Statement of facts” document, which is compiled on board during the course of loading and/or unloading operations.

Table 5. Data obtained from “Statement of facts” document.

Variable	Identifying Characteristic
Port	Loading/Unloading port
Day Month Year	Date of loading or unloading operation
Opening time	Opening time of the cargo space to start loading or unloading operation
Closing time	Closing time of the cargo space to stop loading or unloading operation
Hold	Cargo space or compartment
Complete hold	Cargo hold
Operation	Loading or unloading operation
Complete hold condition	CLOSED (cargo hold closed) OPEN (cargo hold open)

This information is used in the subsequent analysis. To illustrate, if hold 1 is found to be empty and is opened to start loading into compartment 1c, which is in the lower part of the ship’s hold, the process may then begin. Upon completion of the loading process in this compartment, it is closed, the refrigeration process starts, and it is not opened again until the subsequent unloading. Thereafter, the loading process is initiated in compartment 1b, which is completed, and then space 1a is loaded until it is full. The aforementioned hold 1 remains sealed until the subsequent port of call, at which point it will be opened for unloading. Once space 1c is closed, defrosting is initiated, and this affects all of hold 1, even if defrosting is only needed in the lowest compartment. Once a compartment has been definitively closed, the air in it has a high percentage of humidity, and many defrosts are required until the RH drops to about 68%.

Conversely, before the final closure of a compartment, throughout the loading and/or unloading process, during which the compartment is opened and closed for several days, fluctuations in temperature and humidity mean that conditions cannot be stabilised. It was thus deemed appropriate to analyse the data from the final closure of a compartment until its opening for unloading. During this time, the vessel has completed the loading of the holds, travelled to the designated port of discharge and initiated the unloading process.

2.3.2. Data Cleaning and Processing

The data may contain erroneous values because of sensor failure, missing data or the presence of duplicate records. It is essential to detect Not a Number (NaN) values, as these

indicate the presence of missing, unknown or invalid data. The presence of NaN values may influence the descriptive and statistical analysis of variables, resulting in inaccurate results and conclusions. Nonetheless, the detection and proper management of these values help achieve more accurate statistics, thereby enhancing the reliability of the analyses [44]. In the records some of the variables do exhibit NaN values. For instance, T_pulp_1 has 76,608 values, whereas Hour has 76,692. In this instance, it can be concluded that there are invalid data, given that a total of 76,692 observations should have been obtained.

In the cases of T_pulp_6 and T_pulp_7, the NaN values correspond to a lack of data, since not all cargo spaces have the same number of sensors. That is, the corresponding cargo spaces lacked sensors that would otherwise collect data for the aforementioned variables. Given that the number of NaN values identified is relatively low, making up less than 5% of the dataset, the recommended course of action is to delete the records in question, which is a standard approach to dealing with missing data [45,46]. Regarding the cargo space temperature data, the percentage of NaN values is 0.1% for some of the variables. The listwise deletion method is employed, whereby all records containing at least one instance of missing data are eliminated. In our case, the records deleted represent a relatively minor percentage of the entire set of records, and hence their deletion is not considered to have a significant impact on the power or accuracy of the data analysis.

2.3.3. Exploratory Data Analysis

At the outset, graphs are generated for the cooler air temperatures measured, T_return_SB, T_return_PS, T_deliver_SB and T_deliver_PS, for a time interval between 24 h before and 4 h after the start of the defrosting process or event to be analysed, looking for trends in the variables. As the events are analysed, the intervals have been varied to facilitate a more comprehensive understanding of the variables' behaviour. In the light of the data presented in the graphs, it was decided that two new variables should be generated to facilitate the interpretation of the data: the temperature difference between the delivery and return air from the cooler, on both port and starboard sides (Dif_T_PS and Dif_T_SB, respectively). Ultimately, the objective was to ascertain the optimal defrosting parameters by analysing trends in the following variables: T_return_SB, T_return_PS, T_deliver_SB, T_deliver_PS, Dif_T_SB, Dif_T_PS, T_pulp_1, T_pulp_2, T_pulp_3, T_pulp_4, T_pulp_5, T_pulp_6, T_pulp_7 and RH. Furthermore, it was decided that the time axis should be plotted at intervals of 24 h, before and after the start of the event. It is of interest to analyse events that occur after the final closure of the compartments. To this end, the information from the temperature dataframe was combined with that from the closed compartment dataframe. This created a new dataframe, containing data from corresponding to the time when the holds are closed (31,513 out of the initial 76,530, see Table 6).

In a visual analysis of the dataset, graphs obtained by plotting the time series revealed variations of up to 10 °C in some of the recorded parameters, such as T_return and T_pulp, which renders their analysis challenging [47]. In this case study, it is of interest to analyse trends in the records excluding outliers. These values can be attributed to the event itself or instances when cargo spaces have been opened for brief periods to facilitate maintenance or repairs, e.g., a malfunctioning fan. A common practice after compartment closure is to go down to the hold to inspect the condition of the equipment. This also entails opening the compartment, resulting in an influx of external air. It is also noteworthy that the return temperature increases following the completion of the defrost cycle [48]. To deal with outliers, we employed an outlier imputation technique based on median filter time-series signal processing [49], which reduces noise. This is an invaluable technique for processing time-series data when noise reduction is paramount, without compromising the integrity of the underlying signal structure and a preliminary step before the application of predictive

models, as it enhances their accuracy and helps to preserve the essential characteristics of the signals by reducing noise. It was found that the most appropriate course of action was to plot data on the time axis at time intervals between 24 h before and 6 h after the start of the event. This approach enables the identification of loading and unloading operations occurring on the vessel in adjacent compartments and the assessment of their influence on the compartment under study.

Table 6. Extract from the dataframe containing the values of the variables corresponding to the closed compartment scenario.

Variable	Value								
Event	0	1	2	3	...	31,509	31,510	31,511	31,512
Year	2021	2021	2021	2021	...	2022	2022	2022	2022
Month	10	10	10	10	...	2	2	2	2
Day	21	21	21	21	...	28	28	28	28
Hour	18:00	19:00	20:00	21:00	...	13:00	14:00	15:00	20:00
T_return_SB	-11.1	-12.1	4.8	-12.3	...	-15.9	-15.5	-16.9	-17.2
T_return_PS	-11.2	-11.8	9.2	-11.7	...	-17.1	-16.9	-17.6	-17.8
T_deliver_SB	-18.1	-18.3	-18.0	-19.3	...	-17.5	-17.3	-20.6	-21.0
T_deliver_PS	-18.9	-19.4	-19.2	-20	...	-17.2	-17	-20.9	-21.3
T_pulp_1	-4.6	-6.6	-5.6	-7.9	...	-14.5	-14.4	-14.4	-14.5
T_pulp_2	-5.3	-7.3	-6.8	-8.6	...	-13.7	-13.3	-14.2	-14.6
T_pulp_3	-7.8	-9	-7.1	-9.5	...	-14.8	-14.4	-15.9	-16.3
T_pulp_4	-9.1	-10.3	-3.3	-10.5	...	-16.3	-16	-16.9	-17.1
T_pulp_5	-10.2	-10.6	-0.4	-10.8	...	-14.7	-14.4	-15.5	-15.7
T_pulp_6	-7.2	-9.5	-3.1	-9.9	...	-13.4	-13.1	-13.8	-14
T_pulp_7	-0.9	-7	-4.4	-8.2	...	—	—	—	—
RH	80.0	82.4	104.4	83.3	...	77.1	76.9	73.4	73.3
Cargo space *	4c	4c	4c	4c	...	4d	4d	4d	4d
Dif_T_SB	-7	-6.2	-22.8	-7	...	-1.6	-1.8	-3.7	-3.8
Dif_T_PS	-7.7	-7.6	-28.4	-8.3	...	-0.1	-0.1	-3.3	-3.5

Note: “—” indicates missing values in the original dataset; * see Figure 1.

2.4. Machine Learning Classification Framework

This study employs a supervised machine learning approach to classify defrost cycles as necessary (valid) or unnecessary (invalid). The framework comprises four sequential stages: (i) problem formulation and feature engineering; (ii) feature selection; (iii) management of class imbalance and data partitioning; and (iv) training of the model, optimisation and performance evaluation. All computational analyses were performed in Python 3.9.7 using the scikit-learn library [50] and the imbalanced-learn package [51].

2.4.1. Problem Formulation and Theoretical Model

Defrost initiation formulation developed as a supervised binary classification problem, using multivariate operational measurements, is standard in predictive maintenance applications for diagnosis and decision support [52–55].

For each candidate defrost event i , a feature vector x_i as computed from time-series sensor signals preceding the event. The binary target y_i ranged over $\{0,1\}$ and corresponded to CLASE. Specifically, $y_i = 1$ denotes a valid defrost, whereas $y_i = 0$ denotes an invalid defrost. The classifier $f_{\theta}(\cdot)$ is trained to estimate the probability $p_i = P(y_i = 1 | x_i)$. The defrost-on-demand decision is obtained by thresholding p_i with an operational threshold τ , i.e., $\hat{y}_i = I(p_i \geq \tau)$, where τ is selected to balance missed required defrosts against false alarms.

2.4.2. Feature Engineering and Extraction

For each of the monitored variables (T_return_SB, T_return_PS, T_deliver_SB, T_deliver_PS, T_pulp_1–T_pulp_7, RH, Dif_T_SB and Dif_T_PS), nine statistical descriptors were computed over three temporal windows (12, 24 and 36 h prior to defrost initiation, excluding the final hour immediately before the event): mean, median, minimum, maximum, amplitude (max–min), standard deviation, area under the curve (cumulative sum), density (area normalised by window duration) and slope (first-order trend over the window, defined as the end-to-start difference normalised by the window duration).

This feature extraction process yielded an initial feature space of 378 variables (14 variables × 9 descriptors × 3 windows) for 1097 defrost events recorded during the voyage period. After removing instances with missing values, 823 complete observations remained for subsequent analysis, with 337 predictors.

2.4.3. Feature Selection Using Boruta

To address the high dimensionality of the feature space and to identify the most relevant predictors, the Boruta algorithm was employed. In the context of high-dimensional predictive maintenance problems, Boruta has been recommended as a robust wrapper for feature selection as it preserves interpretability while filtering out noisy or redundant sensor-derived predictors [56–58].

The Boruta feature selection was configured with a Random Forest (RF) base estimator (max_depth = 5, class_weight = ‘balanced’, n_jobs = –1, random_state = 7) and executed for 300 iterations (random_state = 16). The algorithm confirmed 38 features as statistically significant and identified 2 tentative features, which were retained for model development, while 289 features were rejected as uninformative. This reduction resulted in a significant decrease from 329 to 40 variables, representing an 87.8% dimensionality reduction.

The selected features (see Table 7) predominantly comprised slope and variability descriptors (standard deviation and amplitude) across the delivery air temperature differential (Dif_T_SB, Dif_T_PS) and delivery air temperatures (T_deliver_SB, T_deliver_PS). This finding indicates that temperature gradient dynamics, rather than absolute values, are the primary indicators of frost accumulation.

Table 7. Features confirmed by Boruta algorithm grouped by temporal window.

Window	Confirmed Features (38 + 2 Tentative)
12 h	T_return_SB_Slope, T_return_PS_Slope, T_deliver_SB_Desv, T_deliver_SB_Slope, T_deliver_PS_Amplitud, T_deliver_PS_Desv, T_deliver_PS_Slope, T_pulp_1_Slope, T_pulp_2_Amplitud, T_pulp_2_Desv, T_pulp_2_Slope, T_pulp_3_Slope, T_pulp_4_Slope, T_pulp_5_Slope, RH_Slope, Dif_T_SB_Amplitud, Dif_T_SB_Desv, Dif_T_SB_Slope, Dif_T_PS_Amplitud, Dif_T_PS_Desv, Dif_T_PS_Slope
24 h	T_deliver_SB_Desv, T_deliver_SB_Slope, T_deliver_PS_Desv, T_deliver_PS_Slope, T_pulp_2_Desv, T_pulp_3_Area, T_pulp_3_Density, T_pulp_4_Slope, Dif_T_SB_Desv, Dif_T_SB_Slope, Dif_T_PS_Desv, Dif_T_PS_Slope
36 h	T_deliver_SB_Slope, T_deliver_PS_Slope, T_pulp_2_Slope, T_pulp_4_Slope, Dif_T_SB_Desv, Dif_T_SB_Slope, Dif_T_PS_Slope

2.4.4. Data Partitioning and Class-Imbalance Handling

The dataset was partitioned using stratified random sampling with an 80:20 train–test split (random_state = 7), thereby ensuring the preservation of class distribution in both subsets. The 80/20 stratified hold-out split is consistent with the findings of recent predictive maintenance studies that have employed supervised learning on industrial time-series [59,60].

To mitigate the negative impact of class imbalance on classifier performance, the SMOTETomek (Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique and Tomek Links) hybrid resampling technique was applied exclusively to the training set, following evidence that hybrid oversampling–cleaning methods such as SMOTETomek improve minority-class detection while controlling noise [61,62]. The training set was balanced with 874 samples (437 per class), whilst the test set retained its original, imbalanced distribution to reflect real operating conditions.

2.4.5. Model Selection

A total of ten algorithms were evaluated in this study, incorporating both traditional classification techniques and ensemble methods.

- Traditional classifiers: Logistic Regression (LR), Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), k-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), Classification and Regression Trees (CART), Gaussian Naïve Bayes (GNB) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) with radial-basis-function (RBF) kernel [63].
- Ensemble methods: Random Forest (RF), AdaBoost (Adaptive Boosting), Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM) and Extra Trees (ET) [64].

The implementation of all models was conducted within standardised pipelines that incorporated z-score normalisation (StandardScaler) as a preprocessing step [65]. The initial model comparison was performed using five-fold stratified cross-validation on the balanced training set, with classification accuracy serving as the primary evaluation metric. The selected set of classifiers is indicative of the prevailing practice in the field of algorithm selection for predictive maintenance studies [54,66].

2.4.6. Performance Evaluation Metrics

Model performance was evaluated using multiple complementary metrics computed on the held-out test set ($n = 165$). The metrics included overall accuracy, precision, recall (sensitivity) and F1-score, in addition to confusion matrices in the conventional form [[TN,FP],[FN,TP]]. Given the operational context, where false negatives (missing a necessary defrost) can lead to cargo temperature deviations, particular emphasis was placed on the recall and F1-score for the positive class (CLASE = 1). In accordance with the findings of recent predictive maintenance studies in the domain of HVAC and compressor monitoring, the positive class was evaluated primarily in terms of the F1-score and recall. These evaluations were complemented by accuracy and confusion matrices [67,68].

3. Results

The results are presented in two stages. Section 3.1 examines the trends observed in the variables before defrosting. Section 3.2 evaluates the performance of the supervised classification model developed to predict defrost validity.

3.1. Pre-Defrost Temperature and Relative Humidity Patterns

We first characterise the pre-defrost behaviour of temperatures and RH:

- Immediately after hold closure, RH is markedly high (85–90%), and frost forms rapidly on the air coolers. Initially, Dif_T serves as an indicator to detect the presence or absence of frost;
- Upon entering conservation mode, RH in the tween deck remains at around 68%;
- After some time with the hold closed, T_deliver and T_return reach similar values, and remain nearly constant, differing by just 1 or 2 °C. Notably, there are no abrupt increases in the variable T_delivery, and consequently, the variable Dif_T changes, for example, from −5 to −3 °C;

- Once the hold has been closed and the temperatures have stabilised, Dif_T approaches 0. This indicates that the temperature in the cargo space does not fall any further, and this is not attributable to frost formation on the heat exchanger;
- Initially, the discrepancy in temperature is observed to be between 10 and 15 °C;
- Once the tween deck in question has been closed for several days, RH drops considerably, resulting in a notable decrease in the aforementioned difference, which reaches values of approximately 1 or 2 °C, and even 0.5 °C in some cases. During these periods, there is no evidence of frost formation on the air coolers. Even when a defrost cycle is initiated, the values remain stable, indicating that this cannot be considered a reliable standard for validating a defrost cycle.

To illustrate this, we analyse the graphs for the event on 7 November at 21:00 (represented by a vertical purple line in the following graphs, Figures 5–11). Compartment 2a had been sealed for only a few hours (16:30–21:00), and two defrost cycles had already been conducted on the same day (02:00, 13:00). Due to a gradual reduction in humidity, as seen in Figure 5, it might have been advisable to increase the time to the next defrost cycle. Although these events are not reflected in the graphs, as the entire hold (compartments 2a, 2b and 2c) is undergoing a defrost cycle, they do influence the conditions. In this instance, the defrost cycle is initiated due to technicians deciding that there was a need to defrost tween decks 2b and 2c. Nonetheless, the temperature readings from the sensors remain stable following the defrosting process (see Figure 6). The behaviour of the variables is satisfactory, even in the absence of a scheduled defrost. The two graphs do not include data from the preceding 24 h, as no data were available for that period. As previously stated, only data recorded since hold no. 2 was closed have been included in the analysis.

Figure 5. Relative humidity (RH) vs. event date and time (compartment 2a).

Figure 6. Bulb sensor temperatures (T_{pulp}) vs. event date and time (compartment 2a).

When compartment 2b had been closed for 3 days (since 4 November at 16:45), the RH is around 78% and tends to increase before the defrost cycle but decrease afterwards (see Figure 7). Additionally, the delivery temperature ($T_{deliver}$) increases before the defrost, which can be attributed to restricted air circulation and reduced heat transfer efficiency within the air cooler, caused by ice accumulation. This trend is observed in both port and starboard coolers (see Figure 8). Therefore, it can be concluded that this defrost is valid.

Figure 7. Relative humidity (RH) vs. event date and time (compartment 2b).

Figure 8. Port and starboard air-cooler return and delivery temperatures (T_{return} and $T_{deliver}$) vs. event date and time (compartment 2b).

Figure 9. Relative humidity (RH) vs. event date and time (compartment 2c).

Figure 10. Port and starboard air-cooler return and delivery temperature difference (Dif_T) vs. event date and time (compartment 2c).

Figure 11. Bulb sensor temperatures (T_{pulp}) vs. event date and time (compartment 2c).

When compartment 2c had been sealed for 16 days (from 22:00 on 22 October), it showed an RH of approximately 70% (see Figure 9). At this stage, Dif_T in this cargo space remains relatively stable, only varying between $-2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-2.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (see Figure 10).

Figure 11 illustrates that the sensor temperatures have reached a state of equilibrium, not affected by defrosting, rendering the defrost process unnecessary in this case.

The loading and unloading of holds have been considered under various conditions (see Table 8), applying the criteria appropriate to each condition to classify a defrost as valid or not. As previously stated, the data have been examined from the start of the loading process to the unloading of the vessel, including the periods of navigation. The following table provides a reference for the following graphs and data tables corresponding to the model event data for each of the labelled subclasses.

Table 8. Possible loading, transport and unloading conditions of the ship for identifying the class and subclass of an event.

Class	Condition	Subclass
Valid defrost (1)	From completion of the loading process and compartment closure until fish transport conditions are reached ($T_{\text{deliver}} \approx -25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\text{RH} \approx 68\%$)	1.1
	After reaching fish transport conditions ($T_{\text{deliver}} \approx -25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\text{RH} \approx 68\%$)	1.2
	Once the atmosphere within the hold has been stable for an extended period of time	1.3
	At the start of loading/unloading from an adjacent compartment	1.4
Not valid defrost (0)	From completion of the loading process and compartment closure until fish transport conditions are reached ($T_{\text{deliver}} \approx -25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\text{RH} \approx 68\%$)	0.1
	After reaching fish transport conditions ($T_{\text{deliver}} \approx -25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\text{RH} \approx 68\%$)	0.2

Criteria used for classifying the defrosts as valid or not valid on observation of the behaviour of port and starboard air-cooler delivery and return temperatures (T_{return} and T_{deliver}), port and starboard air-cooler return and delivery temperature difference (Dif_T), bulb sensor temperatures (T_{pulp}) and relative humidity (RH) are presented below. Information is provided for five events corresponding to each of the indicated subclasses. For the subclass 1.1, graphical representations and tabulated data are provided. The graphs illustrate a 24 h period prior to and 6 h period following the occurrence of the event. The accompanying data are specifically focused on the 6 h preceding the event. For the remaining cases, the criteria used for the classification of defrosting processes are outlined and explicated. The subsequent graphs (Figures 12–17) illustrate the event under analysis as a solid purple line and previous events as a dashed purple line.

3.1.1. Defrosting Was Started 17 h After Compartment Closure (Subclass 1.1)

As illustrated in Figure 12 (compartment 4c), there is a slow decrease in return temperatures alongside a gradual increase in delivery temperatures. The delivery temperature attains the transport condition ($T_{\text{deliver}} \approx -25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) over a period of approximately seven days. The temperature difference decreases; the rate of decrease in return temperature is less pronounced than the rate of increase in delivery temperature. The measurements obtained from bulb sensors within the cargo compartments indicate a gradual reduction in temperature, suggesting that the fish have been stored in the hold for a relatively brief period. Furthermore, sensor data reveal that the cargo spaces are initially loaded at elevated temperatures ranging between $-1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Additionally, the fish exhibit a high moisture content, which may be attributable to freezing in brine. Relative humidity levels within the cargo compartments are around between 80% and 85%.

Table 9 displays the values of the variables recorded for a period of approximately six hours prior to the commencement of the defrosting process. This information, together with that obtained from observing the graphs, allows a better understanding of the behaviour of the variables to be analysed.

Table 9. Variable data in compartment 4c on the 6 h preceding the event in a case of subclass 1.1.

Variable	Value					
Hour	16:00	17:00	18:00	19:00	20:00	21:00
T_return_SB	−14.1	−14.3	−14.2	−14.2	−14.4	−14.4
T_return_PS	−13.5	−13.7	−13.7	−13.8	−13.9	−13.9
T_deliver_SB	−21.6	−22	−20.3	−20.1	−20.3	−20.2
T_deliver_PS	−21.9	−22.4	−21	−20.7	−21.2	−21.1
Dif_T_SB	−7.5	−7.7	−6.1	−5.9	−5.9	−5.8
Dif_T_PS	−8.4	−8.7	−7.3	−6.9	−7.3	−7.2
T_pulp_1	−12.8	−13	−13.2	−13.3	−13.4	−13.5
T_pulp_2	−12.6	−12.9	−13	−13.1	−13.3	−13.4
T_pulp_3	−12.2	−12.4	−12.4	−12.5	−12.5	−12.5
T_pulp_4	−12.4	−12.5	−12.6	−12.7	−12.7	−12.7
T_pulp_5	−12.2	−12.3	−12.2	−12.3	−12.4	−12.5
T_pulp_6	−12.6	−13	−13.1	−13.3	−13.4	−13.4
T_pulp_7	−12.3	−12.8	−13	−13.1	−13.2	−13.3
RH	83	82.5	82.2	82.1	82.1	81.5

Figure 12. Variables vs. event date and time (subclass 1.1). (a). Port and starboard air-cooler return and delivery temperatures (T_{return} and $T_{deliver}$). (b). Port and starboard air-cooler return and delivery temperature difference (Dif_T). (c). Bulb sensor temperatures (T_{pulp}). (d). Relative humidity (RH).

3.1.2. Defrosting Was Started 15 Days After Compartment Closure (Subclass 1.2)

Return temperatures remain stable, while delivery temperatures exhibit an upward trend attributed to ice build-up. This results in a reduced temperature difference, as return temperature remains steady while delivery temperature increases, causing the two temperatures to converge over time. Additionally, the temperature of the bulb sensors in the cargo spaces increase slightly, suggesting that the fish have been stored in the hold for a period exceeding two weeks. This prolonged storage has resulted in substantial moisture loss, leading to a decline in the relative humidity within the hold to approximately 68%. The relative humidity subsequently fluctuates between 68% and 70%, exhibiting a tendency to increase (see Figure 13).

Figure 13. Variables vs. event date and time (subclass 1.2). (a). Port and starboard air-cooler return and delivery temperatures (T_return and T_deliver). (b). Port and starboard air-cooler return and delivery temperature difference (Dif_T). (c). Bulb sensor temperatures (T_pulp). (d). Relative humidity (RH).

3.1.3. Defrosting Carried out 2 Months After Compartment Closure (Subclass 1.3)

Return temperatures remain stable or begin to rise slightly, while delivery temperatures begin to rise, attributable to the onset of ice accumulation. This phenomenon leads to a reduction in the temperature difference, as return temperatures remain constant while delivery temperatures increase. A tendency for temperatures to become more similar, with differences of around -2 to -1 °C, is also observed. The bulb sensors within the cargo spaces also demonstrate stability in their temperature readings, suggesting that the atmosphere within the hold has not yet been significantly subjected to frost accumulation,

as not enough time has elapsed for this to occur. The range of relative humidity is from 66% to 68%, with a slight, non-significant increase observed in humidity before the event (see Figure 14).

Figure 14. Variables vs. event date and time (subclass 1.3). (a). Port and starboard air-cooler return and delivery temperatures (T_{return} and $T_{deliver}$). (b). Port and starboard air-cooler return and delivery temperature difference (Dif_T). (c). Bulb sensor temperatures (T_{pulp}). (d). Relative humidity (RH).

3.1.4. Defrosting Carried out at the Start of Unloading from an Adjacent Compartment in the Same Temperature Zone (Subclass 1.4)

Throughout the observation period, return temperatures remain constant. However, the opening of an adjacent compartment for unloading operations and/or cargo inspection introduces outside air at a higher temperature, leading to an increase in the delivery temperature. This variation is independent of the condition of the fish in the compartment, which remains in optimal transport conditions. Prior to the adjacent compartment opening, the behaviour of the temperature difference is consistent with expected values. Upon opening, the delivery temperature surpasses the return temperature, causing the temperature difference to shift from a negative to a positive value, indicating the onset of condensation

of the moisture present in the atmosphere of the cargo space. The bulb sensors in the cargo compartments record stable temperatures until the entry of warmer external air, at which point a gradual increase in sensor readings is observed. Initially, the relative humidity ranges between 65% and 70%, but a sudden rise in humidity occurs as the warmer air enters the hold, triggering a condensation and freezing process. Subsequent to this, values begin to normalize, with the relative humidity showing a progressive decline over time (see Figure 15).

Figure 15. Variables vs. event date and time (subclass 1.4). (a). Port and starboard air-cooler return and delivery temperatures (T_return and T_deliver). (b). Port and starboard air-cooler return and delivery temperature difference (Dif_T). (c). Bulb sensor temperatures (T_pulp). (d). Relative humidity (RH).

3.1.5. Defrosting Carried out 2 Days After Compartment Closure (Subclass 0.1)

Return temperature displays a gradual decline, following a curve that is appropriate for the circumstances. Similarly, the delivery temperature decreases along a trajectory appropriate for the given conditions. The temperature difference between delivery and return values remains within the expected range. However, during the initial days following the closure of the tween decks, these variables demonstrate an upward trend. Subsequently, the temperatures recorded by the bulb sensors in the cargo spaces progressively decrease, aligning with the prevailing circumstances. Despite these changes, the optimal fish transport conditions ($T_{\text{deliver}} \approx -25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\text{RH} \approx 68\%$) have not yet been achieved. Relative humidity initially remains above 75% but demonstrates a gradual decline over time (see Figure 16).

Figure 16. Variables vs. event date and time (subclass 0.1). (a). Port and starboard air-cooler return and delivery temperatures (T_{return} and T_{deliver}). (b). Port and starboard air-cooler return and delivery temperature difference (Dif_T). (c). Bulb sensor temperatures (T_{pulp}). (d). Relative humidity (RH).

3.1.6. Defrosting Carried out 55 Days After Compartment CLOSURE (Subclass 0.2)

Return temperature remains steady, exhibiting variations only within the expected range after the closure of the compartment. Similarly, delivery temperature maintains consistency, aligning with the optimal conditions for fish transport. The temperature difference between delivery and return remains within the expected range, stabilising at

approximately $-3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ once the plant has reached a state of equilibrium. The bulb sensor readings in the cargo space also remain stable, reflecting the prevailing environmental conditions. Relative humidity is observed to stabilise at around 68%, a level consistent with the dry state of the fish (see Figure 17).

Figure 17. Variables vs. event date and time (subclass 0.2). (a). Port and starboard air-cooler return and delivery temperatures (T_{return} and T_{deliver}). (b). Port and starboard air-cooler return and delivery temperature difference (Dif_T). (c). Bulb sensor temperatures (T_{pulp}). (d). Relative humidity (RH).

In this manner, a table is generated in which the need for the event (defrost) is indicated by a value corresponding to the subclass, thereby obtaining the response or output variable. The final output is enumerated in Table 10. Out of the 1097 defrost processes examined, just 367 have been classified as valid. In other words, the analysis methodology employed suggests that 66.55% of the defrosts would not have been necessary.

Table 10. Extract from the table indicating the output variable “SUBCLASS”.

Date	Compartment	Start Time	Subclass
21 October 2021	4c	20:00	0.1
22 October 2021	4c	4:00	1.1
22 October 2021	4c	14:00	0.1

Table 10. *Cont.*

Date	Compartment	Start Time	Subclass
22 October 2021	4c	22:00	1.1
23 October 2021	4c	12:00	0.1
24 October 2021	4c	12:00	0.1
25 October 2021	4c	10:00	0.1
26 October 2021	4c	11:00	0.1
27 October 2021	4c	11:00	1.1
2 November 2021	4c	10:00	0.2

3.2. Machine Learning Classification Performance

3.2.1. Baseline Model Comparison

Table 11 presents the performance of the ten evaluated classifiers in terms of cross-validation, with the analysis conducted on the balanced training dataset. The findings of this study demonstrate that ensemble methods consistently outperform traditional classifiers. The highest mean training accuracy was achieved by ET (86.84% ± 1.56%), followed by RF (83.07% ± 1.30%) and GBM (82.84% ± 1.22%). Among the conventional methodologies, the SVM exhibited the optimal performance, with an accuracy of 81.46% ± 2.50%.

Table 11. Cross-validation results for baseline classifiers (5-fold stratified CV on balanced training set, n = 874).

Algorithm	CV Accuracy (%) *	Std Dev (%) **	Val. Accuracy (%) ***
LR	78.15	1.39	74.55
LDA	77.57	1.83	76.36
KNN	80.21	1.44	76.97
CART	76.20	3.43	79.39
GNB	65.79	2.23	75.15
SVM	81.46	2.50	79.39
RF	83.07	1.30	82.42
AdaBoost	80.09	1.40	77.58
GBM	82.84	1.22	78.18
ET	86.84	1.56	82.42

* CV Accuracy (%): mean classification accuracy over the five cross-validation folds on the balanced training set. ** Std Dev (%): standard deviation of these five accuracy values. *** Val. Accuracy (%): validation accuracy computed on the resampled training data using the selected model configuration.

The findings of this study demonstrate that tree-based ensembles are particularly well-suited to capture the non-linear interactions and higher-order effects present in the engineered features. This is in line with recent predictive maintenance applications in industrial and HVAC systems [68,69].

3.2.2. Comparative Analysis of Optimised Models

Based on the results, SVM, GBM and ET models were subjected to a process of hyperparameter optimisation using GridSearchCV with StratifiedKFold (three folds). The optimisation metric was set to accuracy for SVM and GBM, whereas ROC-AUC (Receiver Operating Characteristic—Area Under the Curve) was used for the ET model to better account for class imbalance (see Table 12).

The optimisation process evaluated 192 parameter combinations for SVM, 1320 for GBM and 180 for ET. This resulted in 576, 3960 and 540 model fits, respectively, across cross-validation folds.

Table 12. Hyperparameter search space and optimal settings for the tuned classifiers (GridSearchCV).

Model	Hyperparameter	Search Range	Optimal Value
SVM tuned	C	{0.001, 0.005, 0.1, 0.5, 1, 10, 100, 1000}	10
	γ	{1, 0.1, 0.01, 0.005, 0.001, 0.0001}	0.1
	kernel	{rbf, linear, poly, sigmoid}	rbf
GBM tuned	learning_rate	Fixed	0.05
	subsample	{0.55, 0.60, 0.65, 0.75, 0.80, 0.85}	0.75
	n_estimators	{10, 11, . . . , 20}	18
	max_depth	{2, 3, 4, 5}	5
	min_samples_leaf	{5, 10, 1}	5
	random_state	{0}	0
ET tuned	n_estimators	{15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20}	20
	max_depth	{3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8}	8
	min_samples_leaf	{5, 10, 1}	5
	random_state	{0}	0

Table 13 provides a comparison of the validation performance of the tuned classifiers. The operational objective of the present study is to accurately identify required defrost events (CLASE = 1) whilst concurrently minimising superfluous processes. To this end, the study reports precision, recall and F1-score for the positive class, in addition to overall accuracy. SVM achieved perfect training accuracy (100%) but suffered from marked performance degradation on the test set (accuracy 0.745), with an F1-score on CLASE = 1 of only 0.54, indicating overfitting.

Table 13. Validation performance of tuned supervised classifiers for defrost validity prediction.

Model	Accuracy	Precision (CLASE = 1)	Recall (CLASE = 1)	F1-Score (CLASE = 1)	Confusion Matrix [[TN,FP],[FN,TP]]
SVM tuned	0.745	0.52	0.57	0.54	[[98,23],[19,25]]
GBM tuned	0.818	0.71	0.68	0.69	[[101,14],[16,34]]
ET tuned	0.824	0.75	0.68	0.71	[[100,12],[17,36]]

The tuned GBM similarly exhibited a substantial train–test accuracy gap (0.929 vs. 0.818), with test F1-score for CLASE = 1 of 0.69, whereas the tuned ET classifier demonstrated a more modest gap (0.862 vs. 0.824) and the best F1-score on the positive class (0.713).

4. Discussion

4.1. Main Findings

The exploratory analysis of pre-defrost temperature and relative humidity patterns provides important physical context for the classification results. The subclass-based labelling procedure demonstrates that, under the observed operating conditions, only 367 of 1097 recorded defrost cycles were thermodynamically justified according to the trends in delivery and return air temperatures (T_{deliver}, T_{return}), temperature differentials (Dif_T), pulp temperatures (T_{pulp}) and relative humidity (RH). This suggests that 66.55% of cycles could have been safely deferred. The criteria derived for each subclass consistently indicate that valid defrosts are associated with sustained increases in air temperature differentials and humidity, together with loss of cooling effectiveness prior to the event, whereas non-valid defrosts occur when these variables remain relatively stable and within acceptable ranges. The findings support the selection of slope- and variability-based

features from these signals for the supervised learning stage, and explain why the tuned ET model is able to discriminate necessary from unnecessary defrosts using only standard shipboard sensor data.

From a product quality perspective, these temperature and humidity patterns are directly linked to the preservation of frozen tuna and other fish products. The regulatory guidelines stipulated for frozen fish require that the product must be maintained at a stable temperature of either $-18\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ or below during both the transport and storage periods. This allows only brief fluctuations within a narrow margin [69]. Sustained increases in hold and pulp temperatures, or repeated temperature oscillations, have been shown to accelerate biochemical and microbiological processes, including histamine formation in tuna. This, in turn, can compromise product quality and safety. Likewise, relative humidity levels influence both microbial growth and surface dehydration. An excess of moisture, in conjunction with an inadequate defrost management strategy, has been shown to encourage the accumulation of ice, impede air circulation and compromise the uniformity of cooling [12]. The pre-defrost trends described in Figures 3–15 serve as indicative indicators of frosting on the air coolers. Furthermore, these trends are also indicative of conditions that may favour or hinder the maintenance of product quality during the voyage [8].

The pre-defrost trends identified in this work are consistent with the expected thermodynamic behaviour of frosted air coolers. As frost accumulation increases, thermal resistance and reduced airflow effectiveness are observed, resulting in a deterioration of the delivery–return temperature relationship and an increase in the air-side temperature differential (Dif_T). From a control perspective, humidity-related indicators provide complementary evidence of frosting propensity under variable operating conditions. These observations support the long-standing view that fixed timer-based or timing–temperature defrost strategies [18,24] can trigger premature or unnecessary cycles when operating conditions fluctuate, particularly in humid environments. In comparison with conventional approaches that are widely implemented in practice, the proposed framework formalises defrost demand using multivariate patterns derived from standard onboard measurements (temperatures and RH). This approach is better suited to variable maritime conditions.

In contrast to many on-demand defrost methods that rely on specialised sensing (e.g., pressure-drop, optical/frost-thickness or image-based techniques) and are often validated primarily in controlled environments [26–29], the present approach is designed for deployment in an operating reefer plant using existing instrumentation, without hardware modifications. Industrial adaptive controllers have the capacity to cancel scheduled defrosts based on proxy indicators (e.g., airflow disruption). Similarly, the classifier developed here provides an evidence-based decision rule that distinguishes required from avoidable defrost events under real shipboard conditions. This comparison elucidates the contribution of the present work as a low-barrier, shipboard-validated step towards defrost-on-demand decision support in reefer-ship refrigeration systems.

In the context of the tuned candidates (SVM, GBM and ET), the tuned Extra Trees (ET) model is identified as the most suitable classifier for defrost-on-demand scheduling. This is due to the fact that it provides the strongest performance on the critical class (CLASE = 1, required/valid defrost) while exhibiting the best generalisation behaviour. In this particular application, the minority/critical class is operationally decisive: false negatives (FNs) correspond to missed required defrost events and therefore represent the highest-risk error mode, whereas false positives (FPs) correspond to unnecessary defrost triggers and mainly affect energy consumption and process disturbance.

In the hold-out validation set, the ET model attains the maximum F1-score for CLASE = 1 (F1 = 0.71). The elevated F1-score is indicative of an equilibrium between

precision (0.75) and recall (0.68) for the requisite defrost class. This outcome surpasses that of the SVM model ($F1 = 0.54$) and marginally exceeds that of the GBM model ($F1 = 0.69$). In practice, the ET model identifies the majority of the necessary defrosts in comparison to competing models, thereby reducing the likelihood of defrost demand being overlooked.

The model's training accuracy has been determined to be 0.862, while its test accuracy has been found to be 0.824. It is important to note that these two accuracy levels are only separated by a margin of 3.8 percentage points, suggesting effective generalisation capabilities of the model. In contrast, the SVM tuned model achieves a perfect score of 1.000 in the training phase, but exhibits a decline to 0.745 in the testing phase, resulting in a discrepancy of 25.5 points. Similarly, the GBM tuned model experiences a reduction in performance, from 0.929 to 0.818, indicating a more significant overfitting issue in both models.

In a defrost-on-demand system [70], it is imperative to minimise both missed defrosts (FNs) and unnecessary defrosts (FPs). The ET tuned profile (FN = 17, FP = 12) reflects a more reasonable operational compromise than SVM and GBM, which either overfit or sacrifice more performance in testing. Furthermore, the ET tuned configuration (extremely randomized forest with limited depth and `min_samples_leaf = 5`) functions as explicit regularisation, thereby mitigating the risk of memorising specific voyage patterns and promoting more stable behaviour in future routes and load conditions.

4.2. Limitations and Practical Applications

Despite the unavailability of direct energy metering for the quantification of savings in kWh, the proposed framework identified 66.55% of recorded defrost cycles as non-required under the studied operating conditions. This provides a quantitative proxy indicating substantial potential for reduced defrost-related energy use, which will be quantified in future work by linking avoided defrost operations to measured or logged power/thermal data.

The study is also limited by the fact that most events correspond to conditions with cargo holds predominantly closed, so model performance under prolonged open-hold operation remains to be assessed. Moreover, the current dataset did not include marine environmental variables such as seawater temperature, ambient air temperature and its RH. The incorporation of these variables in future work may enhance the comprehension of external drivers of defrost demand. In the present implementation, the influence of the marine environment is therefore captured only indirectly through its effect on hold temperature, humidity and air-cooler behaviour. A more explicit theoretical treatment would require the use of seawater temperature, ambient air temperature and external humidity as exogenous inputs, thereby improving model robustness under varying routes and seasons.

From a practical perspective, the proposed approach can be implemented as a decision-support instrument for chief engineers and ship operators, highlighting defrost cycles that are likely to be unnecessary and helping to prioritise interventions. The framework's deployment is not contingent on hardware modifications due to its reliance on standard temperature and humidity sensors that are already installed on board. In principle, this framework can be extended to other reefer ships and refrigeration plants, thereby facilitating the gradual adoption of data-driven Refrigeration 4.0 practices in maritime operations.

Although this study was developed and validated within the specific context of the frozen tuna supply chain, the proposed methodology can be extended to other refrigerated cargoes and refrigeration plants. Indeed, the refrigeration system of the vessel has been designed to transport chilled products, such as bananas at $+12\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and fruit at $+1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Consequently, defrosting remains an operational necessity whenever moisture ingress and

temperatures result in ice accumulation. The approach is based on sensor data and the dynamic behaviour of evaporators; the same data-driven framework can, in principle, be extended to other cargoes transported under similar refrigeration and frozen configurations. For deployment in a new cargo, the labelling criteria and model are recalibrated and validated to reflect the new operating conditions.

5. Conclusions

This study presents an innovative predictive maintenance framework based on big data analysis and ML techniques. The objective of the tool is to optimise defrost cycles in refrigeration plants of reefer ships using only real-world operational sensor data, in contrast to previous defrost-control studies conducted in laboratory settings or stationary installations. The proposed model employs a supervised machine-learning classifier to classify defrost events as valid/required (CLASE = 1) or invalid/non-required (CLASE = 0). Following a comprehensive analysis of the ten algorithms, a decision was made to optimise three of them (SVM, GBM, ET). The Extra Trees algorithm offers the most favourable balance for operational use, attaining an accuracy of 0.824 and the highest F1-score of 0.71 for the critical class (CLASE = 1). It also demonstrates the most robust generalisation behaviour on the hold-out validation set.

This innovative strategy facilitates the identification of unnecessary defrost cycles. Specifically, the results showed that approximately three-quarters (66.55%) of the defrost cycles conducted during the study period could have been avoided, highlighting potential energy savings, operational optimisation and lifespan prolongation of equipment.

The strategy of defrost cycle control is notable for its adaptability to the variable conditions present in the maritime environment, where factors such as humidity and temperature in the ship's holds exhibit significant fluctuations depending on the ship's cargo or operational status, including loading and unloading.

From an operational and managerial perspective, the proposed framework offers a practical path to transition from manually triggered, experience-based defrost decisions towards data-driven, event-based control. This approach anticipates defrost needs, reduces unnecessary manual inspections of cargo holds and is cost-effective for shipowners because it relies on standard instrumentation already installed on board. The model outputs can be used by technical departments to define new defrost policies. This will support more informed maintenance and energy management decisions. These findings build on existing work on predictive maintenance and adaptive defrost control in commercial refrigeration and HVAC systems, extending such concepts to the specific context of reefer vessels.

Future work will focus on (i) extending the analysis to operating periods with cargo holds open (e.g., loading/unloading) to characterise model robustness under humidity and thermal variability; (ii) validating the selected classifier on new voyages and unseen data to assess transferability; (iii) performing a quantitative assessment of energy efficiency, linking avoided defrost operations to energy consumption and associated emissions using measured or logged power/thermal data; and (iv) incorporating marine environmental variables, including but not limited to seawater and ambient air temperatures, to better characterise external drivers of defrost demand.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

AdaBoost	Adaptive Boosting
AI	Artificial Intelligence
COP	Coefficient of Performance
CART	Classification and Regression Trees
ET	Extra Trees
FN	False Negative
FP	False Positive
GBM	Gradient Boosting Machine
GNB	Gaussian Naïve Bayes
KNN	k-Nearest Neighbours
LDA	Linear Discriminant Analysis
LR	Logistic Regression
MGO	Medium Gas Oil
ML	Machine Learning
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning
IoT	Internet of Things
RBF	Radial Basis Function
RF	Random Forest
RH	Relative Humidity
ROC-AUC	Receiver Operating Characteristic–Area Under the Curve
SMOTETomek	Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique and Tomek Links
SVM	Support Vector Machine

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